

Cerebral Cortex Empathic Theory

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2 Neurons MM which are very small make thousand
20,000 Neurons . 2 mm makes up 6km of neighbors
of connect messages in the brain.

20,000 NEURONS

Above (Left) is Neurons and dendrites in the brain.
Below (Right) how information passes and the brain
Network.

This gives interconnected network communication.

Associate Memory (AM)

Read this Message!

It is soo a*esome that w*at your *ind and e*es can
s*e is ab le to read *nd un*ersta*d this witho*t
a** of the in*orm*tion le*tters

The processing and memory are connected, they are
not separated.

